

WP3 - Accounting for agroforestry benefits: tools for beneficiaries of agroforestry products and services

Monitoring Soil Health in Agroforestry Systems: A Guide to Assessment

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Executive Summary

The DigitAF research project (July 2022 to June 2026), funded by the European Commission, aims at a high-quality implementation of agroforestry to foster climate change mitigation and adaptation in agriculture and to ensure sustainable management of natural resources. The goal was to provide the main actor groups with tools, digital tools in particular, capable of meeting their needs. The three actors' groups that are targeted by DigitAF are:

- **Policy actors:** policymakers and administrations concerned with applying agroforestry-related regulations, at regional, national and European levels, who set the scene for the adoption (or not) of agroforestry.
- **Practitioners:** farmers, landowners, and by extension, farm advisers playing an active role in designing and managing agroforestry systems and whose choices determine the agronomic, economic, environmental, and social performance at farm-level and beyond.
- **Beneficiaries** of agroforestry products and services are other stakeholders in the value chain, including wholesalers, retailers, organisations trading the carbon sequestration and biodiversity benefits of agroforestry, and final consumers seeking verification of the benefits of agroforestry in clear and accessible terms.

One output of the project is a study of methods for determining and accounting for soil health and greenhouse gas emissions within agroforestry systems (den Herder et al., 2026). The first half of that report describes the measurement and reporting of soil health across seven sites in Czechia, Finland, Italy, Portugal, Spain, the Netherlands, and the United Kingdom. The report that you are reading now was initially developed as an Annex to that report.

The objective of this Annex report is to provide a harmonised guide that covers (i) sampling design in spatially heterogeneous agroforestry systems (isolated trees, row-based alley cropping, and area-based systems), (ii) field measurement protocols for a core indicator set spanning chemical, physical, and biological soil health dimensions, and (iii) laboratory analysis, calculation, and reporting steps. The core soil health indicators prioritised within WP3 include soil organic carbon (SOC) and soil pH (chemical), bulk density (physical), and earthworm abundance as a practical soil fauna indicator (biological), consistent with a previous produced Milestone report on DigitAF Methods for Carbon and Soil Health Assessments (den Herder et al., 2024). Where resources allow, the guide also provides options to extend monitoring to microbial indicators such as bacteria and fungi, improving the completeness of soil biological assessment.

By standardising field procedures (including plot set-up, composite sampling, depth increments, labelling, and metadata capture), and by clarifying how to calculate SOC stocks under varying bulk density and coarse fragment conditions, the guide supports credible, repeatable reporting for both science and practice. This includes practical guidance on when to use fixed-depth versus equivalent soil mass approaches, and how to document site history and management to strengthen interpretation and comparability. Ultimately, this annex enables DigitAF partners and stakeholders to generate robust, comparable soil health evidence that can be integrated with broader agroforestry accounting and verification efforts, and that can support transparent communication of agroforestry benefits to value-chain actors, certification schemes, and policy processes, including those linked to soil health targets and climate reporting under the United Nations Framework Convention for Climate Change (UNFCCC).

1. Introduction

1.1. Context

The Intergovernmental Technical Panel on Soils (ITPS) defines soil health as “the ability of the soil to sustain the productivity, diversity, and environmental services of terrestrial ecosystems” (FAO, 2020b). It encompasses biological, physical, and chemical factors, recognizing the soil as a dynamic, living system. Key indicators of soil health include organic matter content, soil structure, nutrient availability, microbial activity, and water infiltration. Healthy soils support diverse biological communities, cycle nutrients efficiently, retain moisture, and resist erosion, all while contributing to environmental resilience and mitigating challenges such as climate change by sequestering carbon and filtering water. Soil health is vital for agricultural productivity, biodiversity, and the long-term sustainability of ecosystems.

Measurements of soil health can be a useful in guiding management practices to maintain and improve soil health. By assessing various indicators, we can detect problems early and implement targeted management practices to restore soil fertility, improve water retention, and support carbon sequestration services (Lehmann et al., 2020). Because soil health is determined by a range of characteristics, comprehensive monitoring of soil health requires a range of measurements. In a study examining the integration of agroforestry into national monitoring, reporting and verification (MRV) systems under the UNFCCC, it was found that while many countries recognize the benefits of agroforestry, significant gaps exist in its measurement and reporting, particularly regarding soil carbon and tree-based systems (Rosenstock et al., 2019). Cardinael et al. (2025) also report that many research studies on carbon sequestration in agroforestry systems do not fulfil simple requirements that would ensure the scientific value of those studies.

Recent policy developments further underline the need for standardised, comparable soil data. The EU Directive on Soil Monitoring and Resilience calls for a coherent, harmonised approach to monitoring and assessing soil health, requiring the use of common descriptors (physical, chemical, biological) and an EU methodology to guide sampling, explicitly to strengthen monitoring capacity and improve data comparability (European Commission, 2023). This is particularly important for soil organic carbon assessment, because SOC stocks and persistence are influenced not only by land use and management, but also by pedo-climatic conditions, mineralogical and geochemical controls, and soil depth, which can affect how SOC changes are interpreted across sites and over time (von Fromm et al., 2024). In this context, harmonised protocols are useful not only for scientific comparability across sites and years, but also for generating evidence that is credible for reporting, advisory services, and decision support.

This guideline aims to provide a harmonized approach to guide the assessment of different agroforestry practices on soil health across agroforestry living labs in Europe, within the framework of the DigitAF project. By generating robust and reliable evidence on soil health, this guideline can be used to facilitate informed decision-making regarding agroforestry practices and policies in the study region. The guide includes protocols for each step of the process, beginning with sampling design, which outlines the approach for selecting representative sites. It covers field sampling techniques to ensure accurate and consistent data collection across varying environmental conditions. Additionally, the guide provides guidelines for laboratory analysis to assess key soil health indicators, followed by comprehensive data analysis methods to interpret the results. The SOC assessment and reporting procedures presented in this guide can also support wider land degradation neutrality and sustainable

land management reporting, provided that sampling design, bulk density, coarse fragments, soil depth and uncertainty are reported transparently (Chotte et al., 2019).

1.2. What is a healthy soil?

Healthy soil is a dynamic system where chemical, physical, and biological factors interact to support robust plant growth, maintain ecosystem health, and contribute to overall environmental sustainability (Lehmann et al., 2020) (Table 1).

Table 1. Key chemical, physical, and biological characteristics of healthy soils.

Soil characteristics	Key features
Chemical	<p>Nutrient content: Balanced levels of nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium, calcium, magnesium, and sulphur.</p> <p>pH level: Optimal range (6.0 to 7.5) for nutrient availability. Extreme pH affects nutrient uptake and biology.</p> <p>Organic matter: Improves soil fertility, structure, and provides nutrients.</p>
Physical	<p>Texture: Balanced mix of sand, silt, and clay for water retention, drainage, and aeration.</p> <p>Structure: Crumbly, granular texture with well-defined aggregates for root penetration and water infiltration.</p> <p>Water holding capacity: Retains moisture but drains excess to prevent waterlogging.</p>
Biological	<p>Microbial activity: High levels of bacteria, fungi, and microorganisms for nutrient cycling and organic matter decomposition.</p> <p>Soil fauna: Earthworms, ants, and beetles improve aeration, organic matter breakdown, and nutrient availability.</p> <p>Soil biodiversity: Diverse microbial and faunal community enhances resilience and function.</p>

1.3. Major soil health constraints

Soil health is crucial for sustainable agriculture and environmental conservation, yet many regions in Europe face significant challenges that impact soil quality. According to the European Union Soil Observatory (EUSO), about 62% of soil in the European Union (EU) is classified as unhealthy (Panagos et al., 2024) costing over €50 billion per year due to the loss of essential services and to the impact on human health (Panagos et al., 2025). The major soil degradation processes include, among others, soil erosion, loss of soil organic carbon (SOC), nutrient losses, decline in soil biodiversity, salinization, soil compaction, contamination, and soil sealing. For example, De Rosa et al. (2024) found that the conversion of grazing lands into croplands is a major cause of SOC depletion. These constraints affect soil's ability to support plant growth, maintain ecosystem functions, and withstand environmental stresses (van Noordwijk et al., 2023). Understanding these challenges is essential for developing effective strategies to improve soil health and ensure long-term agricultural productivity and ecological balance (Table 2).

Addressing the constraints and impacts involves adopting sustainable land management practices, improving soil fertility management, and enhancing soil conservation interventions. It also requires integrated soil management practices, restoration efforts, and policies that promote sustainable land use and conservation strategies to enhance soil health, support climate resilience, and sustain ecosystems and communities.

Table 2. Overview of soil health constraints across chemical, physical, and biological categories, along with their contributing causes and major impacts on agricultural productivity, environmental sustainability, water management, climate resilience, and socio-economic conditions.

Character	Constraint	Causes	Major Impacts
Chemical	Nutrient deficiency	Intensive farming: Continuous cropping depletes soil nutrients. Poor soil management practices: Lack of crop rotation and cover cropping reduces nutrient replenishment.	Reduced agricultural productivity: Decreased crop yields, lower food security. Dependency on external inputs: Increased fertilizer use.
	Soil acidity/alkalinity	Natural soil conditions: Some regions have naturally acidic or alkaline soils due to geological formations. Acid rain: Industrial activities and biomass burning contribute to soil acidification.	Environmental degradation: Soil erosion, desertification, loss of fertility. Water management challenges: Increased runoff and flooding.
	Low organic matter	Deforestation: Loss of vegetation reduces organic matter inputs. Inadequate organic amendments: Limited use of compost or manure. Erosion: Erosion depletes the topsoil where organic matter is concentrated.	Environmental degradation: Increased erosion and desertification. Climate Impacts: Reduced carbon sequestration, increased greenhouse gas emissions.
Physical	Poor soil texture	Erosion: Wind and water erosion depletes finer soil particles. Compaction: Overgrazing and heavy machinery use lead to soil compaction. Unsustainable land use: Improper irrigation can lead to salinization	Water management challenges: Reduced water retention, exacerbating drought impacts. Increased runoff and flooding: Poor water absorption.
	Weak soil structure	Erosion: Disrupts soil aggregation and structure. Compaction: Soil compaction from machinery or overgrazing impairs structure. Low organic matter: Insufficient organic matter affects soil aggregation	Environmental degradation: Soil erosion, loss of soil fertility. Water management challenges: Poor water retention.
	Inadequate water holding capacity	Desertification: Overgrazing and deforestation reduce water holding capacity. Poor soil management: Inefficient irrigation practices and inadequate soil conservation.	Water management challenges: Reduced moisture retention, exacerbating drought. Climate Impacts: Increased water runoff and flooding.
Biological	Low microbial activity	Low organic matter: Reduces microbial food sources. Extreme pH levels: Inhibits microbial activity. Chemical inputs: Excessive use of chemicals negatively impacts microbial life.	Loss of biodiversity: Reduced soil biodiversity, affecting nutrient cycling. Economic and social impacts: Reduced crop productivity and farm profitability.
	Reduced soil fauna	Erosion and compaction: Disrupts habitats for soil fauna. Chemical use: Pesticides and chemicals harm soil organisms. Deforestation: Reduces habitat and food sources for soil fauna	Loss of biodiversity: Disruption of soil ecosystems, reduced habitat for wildlife. Economic impacts: Reduced agricultural productivity.
	Low soil biodiversity	Monoculture farming: Reduces habitat diversity. Soil degradation: Erosion, compaction, and contamination reduce biodiversity. Inadequate conservation practices: Lack of sustainable practices leads to decline in biodiversity.	Loss of biodiversity: Disruption of ecosystem balance, decline in beneficial soil organisms. Climate impacts: Reduced carbon sequestration and nutrient cycling

2. Soil health monitoring for agroforestry systems

2.1. DigitAF Project Living Labs

Six living labs plus two additional sites spread over eight countries have case study farms involved in the DigitAF project. The location of these case studies are illustrated in Figure 1. The farms are situated across a diverse agroecological regions and represent different environmental, social, and agricultural contexts. By engaging with a variety of ecosystems and farming systems, the project aims to foster cross-country collaboration and knowledge exchange to advance sustainable agroforestry practices across Europe.

Figure 1. The eight agroforestry case study farms across eight European countries involved in the DigitAF project. The red dots represent the locations of these case study farms.

2.2. Sampling design

The spatial variability in soil characteristics should be critically considered in designing a sampling scheme. The high spatial variability of soil characteristics occurs both a site, farm, and landscape scales and it hinders the ability to accurately measure and account for changes in, for example, stocks of soil carbon relevant to farm- and national inventories and emissions trading schemes. Sampling designs commonly used in biophysical sciences are summarized in Figure 2. Refer to de Gruijter et al. (2006) for more details on sampling designs. In the following sections, we provide an overview of various agroforestry design types, followed by a simplified workflow that outlines the key steps involved in estimating soil health properties. This workflow, illustrated in Figure 2, demonstrates the major steps involved in estimating soil health properties, with soil organic carbon (SOC) used as an example. It highlights each stage, from initial data collection to final analysis, offering a clear framework for understanding how soil health properties can be assessed in agroforestry systems.

Figure 2. Workflow illustrating the major steps involved in estimating soil health properties, with soil organic carbon used as an example.

2.3. Guide for carbon stock quantification and reporting in agroforestry

The guidelines for quantification and reporting of carbon stocks in agroforestry systems by Cardinael et al. (2025) provide a useful resource for ensuring consistent and accurate carbon accounting in agroforestry systems. Below, we summarize the key points outlining the parameters and recommended practices for designing, implementing, and reporting carbon assessments. The objective is to promote transparency, comparability, and consistency across studies. For agroforestry systems with livestock or grazing components, the FAO LEAP guidelines provide complementary guidance for measuring and modelling soil organic carbon stocks and stock changes in livestock production systems, including baseline definition, sampling design, modelling and uncertainty reporting (FAO, 2019).

Table 3 provides a summary of the main parameters and recommended practices for the consistent sampling, site description, and reporting of carbon stocks. By adhering to these guidelines, studies can improve the comparability and accuracy of carbon sequestration estimates across diverse agroforestry practices. The table covers sampling design, soil and biomass carbon measurement techniques, and site-specific contextual factors. Furthermore, it underscores the importance of detailed management practices and environmental conditions that influence carbon storage dynamics.

Table 3. Framework for carbon quantification and reporting in agroforestry (Cardinael et al., 2025).

Reporting element	Description / Implementation
Sampling design	
Controlling soil spatial heterogeneity	Agroforestry systems are spatially heterogeneous, and this variability must be reflected in the sampling design when assessing SOC stocks (Bayala et al., 2007; Cardinael et al., 2015). While no standard methodology exists, designs may include transects across tree lines, circular plots around individual trees, or other system-specific approaches (Minarsch et al., 2024).
How to deal with replication vs pseudoreplications	Agroforestry systems are often large-scale and difficult to study using standard block designs due to spatial heterogeneity, which can obscure results even when replication is possible. Most studies rely on comparisons between an agroforestry and a control plot, using pseudoreplications to capture intra-system variability (Cardinael et al., 2025). While this limits the strength and extrapolation of conclusions—especially in synchronic or chronosequence studies with few plots—pseudoreplications can be accounted for using statistical models like linear mixed-effects models (Cardinael et al., 2025). Authors should acknowledge these limitations and avoid overgeneralized claims based on limited data, though such studies still provide valuable insights for meta-analyses and broader syntheses based on networks of paired-site experiments.
Frequency and timing of sampling	It is recommend collecting soil samples at time 0—prior to tree planting—even if immediate SOC analysis isn’t possible, as samples can be air-dried and analyzed later. This enables diachronic studies and improves estimates of additional carbon storage by minimizing confounding effects. If baseline samples are missing, diachronic comparisons can still be made between later dates (e.g., year 3 and year 10), though meaningful SOC changes often require 5–10 years to detect (Smith, 2004). Early changes may be seen in soil fractions or parameters, but seasonal and management-related fluctuations mean sampling should always occur at the same time across treatments and years, with sampling dates clearly reported.
Site description	
Precise GPS coordinates	The exact location of the agroforestry study sites must be provided. Firstly, because of transparency and reproducibility of the study as well as enabling follow-up studies to investigate long-term effects. Secondly, because an absence of precise GPS coordinates prevents study site identification in aerial imagery or their use as training data for spatial modelling efforts.

	At least to 3 decimal places of coordinate precision (e.g., 3.704°N, 3.862°E): As a reminder, one decimal place (0.1 degrees) is equivalent to a precision of 11.1 km, two decimal places/ (0.01 degrees) to 1.11 km, three decimal places. (0.001) to 111 m.
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Site description (continued)	
Pedo-climatic context:	To compare systems and assess potential SOC stock changes, it is essential to report soil type, texture, bulk density, pH, slope, and basic climate data (mean annual rainfall and temperature, Köppen climate classification, and elevation). Soil texture significantly affects carbon sequestration potential and is closely linked to SOC concentration and saturation. Agroforestry can also reduce erosion—particularly on slopes (Zhu et al., 2020) — indirectly enhancing SOC stocks through apparent sequestration.
Study site history	Study site history is often poorly reported, yet it is critical for interpreting SOC stock changes in agroforestry systems, especially when comparing to non-agroforestry systems. This is due to the need for large, representative agroforestry plots, the frequent use of chronosequences instead of long-term trials, and the historical placement of land uses in specific landscape positions (e.g., forests on slopes, crops on fertile flats). Ideally, SOC should be measured at system establishment, but in false time series, this is often missing—so data from historically managed neighboring sites should be provided. Additionally, information on adjacent land management practices is valuable for context.
Basic carbon components	
Carbon content or concentration of biomass and soil	Often expressed in percent (%), but following international units it should be in g C kg ⁻¹
C stocks	A stock represents an amount of carbon usually per unit of area, for instance Mg C ha ⁻¹ or kg C m ⁻² , and in case of SOC to a defined soil depth. It can also be expressed per individual tree in the case of biomass, for instance kg C tree ⁻¹ , and sometimes per unit of length, for instance in the case of hedgerows (Mg C km ⁻¹).
Carbon sequestration	involves a time factor, it is a rate process, and the age of the system is needed to calculate this rate. The unit is then Mg C ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹
Reporting soil carbon	
Soil bulk density	Soil bulk density (g cm ⁻³ or kg m ⁻³) should be measured across all treatments and depths alongside SOC measurements. Stone content (> 2 mm) must be accounted for to avoid overestimating SOC stocks (Poeplau et al., 2017), and the absence of stones should be explicitly stated.
SOC concentration	Dumas dry combustion method (FAO, 2020a) is recommend measuring SOC concentration. In cases like calcareous soils, inorganic carbon should be removed—typically through acidification with 0.5 M HCl (Oelbermann et al., 2006) or acid fumigation (Cardinael et al., 2015).
Using the equivalent soil mass approach	Soil bulk density varies with system type and management practices, yet many studies still compare SOC stocks at fixed depths, which can lead to misleading conclusions. To accurately compare SOC in agroforestry systems with reference plots (e.g., cropland, grassland, or forest), differences in bulk density must be accounted for using the equivalent soil mass (ESM) approach (Huete, Justice and Leeuwen, 1999; McBratney and Minasny, 2010; Wendt and Hauser, 2013; Lee-Smith et al., 2020; Fowler et al., 2023).
Approaches and reference in space and time	To assess agroforestry impacts on SOC stocks, different approaches can be used: Attend the 2025 Africa Food Systems Forum (August 31 – September 5, Senegal). The diachronic approach—sampling the same plots over time—is the most accurate (Bernoux et al., 2005; Leng et al., 2024), but often impractical as it requires baseline data at planting. The more commonly used synchronic method compares adjacent plots under different systems; however, it is frequently

misapplied and only valid when key conditions are met, particularly identical soils and land-use histories prior to implementation.

Reporting soil carbon (continued)	
Soil depth	The IPCC recommends sampling soils to at least 30 cm, yet many studies still focus only on the top 20 cm. For harmonised DigitAF topsoil monitoring, the standard reporting depth is 0–20 cm, consistent with LUCAS and LDSF topsoil protocols. This does not prevent studies from collecting additional deeper layers where resources allow, especially in agroforestry systems where tree roots may influence deeper soil processes. However, deeper layers should be collected, analysed and reported separately from the standard 0–20 cm topsoil layer, using clearly stated depth increments such as 20–30 cm or 20–50 cm (Mulia and Dupraz, 2006; Haile et al., 2010; Upson and Burgess, 2013; Cardinael et al., 2017; Shi et al., 2018; Siegwart et al., 2023).
Reporting biomass carbon	
Using the right allometric equations	Destructive sampling provides the most accurate biomass estimates but is rarely used in agroforestry due to the need to cut trees on farms, so aboveground biomass is typically estimated using allometric equations based on DBH, tree height, and sometimes wood density—authors should at least report DBH, and ideally also tree height and basal area by species. Because biomass estimates can be sensitive to the way tree height–diameter relationships are modelled, especially in mixed-species woodland and agroforestry contexts, studies should clearly report whether tree height was measured or modelled and describe the equations used for biomass estimation (Valbuena et al., 2016). Root biomass is even harder to assess directly due to variability and depth; while emerging tools like ground-penetrating radar show promise (Borden et al., 2014), most estimates still rely on root:shoot ratios with high uncertainty. Studies report the source of the allometric equations that are used and the context in which they were developed in addition to a statement on the limitations of using those allometric equations.
Agroforestry trees also benefit from agricultural inputs	Agroforestry trees also benefit from agricultural inputs including fertilizers, manure, addition of tree prunings as mulch, and they usually grow faster than trees in forests (Balandier and Dupraz, 1999). It is important to such observations.
Biomass carbon concentration	Although many studies assume wood contains 50% carbon, this varies by species, site conditions, and even within the tree, so measuring carbon concentration—ideally via the Dumas dry combustion method (FAO, 2020a)—is recommended. If direct measurement is not possible, refined default values based on region (e.g., tropical, temperate) or tree type (conifer/deciduous) should be used (Thomas and Martin, 2012). Species-specific data for both biomass carbon concentration and wood density are also available in the TRY global database of plant traits (Kattge et al., 2011).
Documentation of carbon inputs to the soil	To advance from simple carbon stock accounting to a more process-based understanding of C dynamics, more detailed data are needed—though often lacking due to the effort involved. Aboveground carbon inputs (e.g., litter, manure, crop residues) can be directly measured, while belowground inputs (e.g., root mortality) can be estimated using root:shoot ratios. Detailed monitoring of tree and crop management, including crop yields, is essential for estimating these inputs. Such estimates improve our understanding of C dynamics and help disentangle input, decomposition, and stabilization processes, especially when used with process-based models (Laub et al., 2018; Lamichhane, Kumar and Wilson, 2019). Estimating the conversion rate of organic inputs to SOC is also valuable for system comparisons.
Agroforestry design and management practices:	A detailed characterization of the agroforestry system is crucial, especially when reporting carbon accumulation rates. This should include system age, tree rotations (number and duration), tree density, species (common and Latin names), and

abundance. Key management information—such as planting density, thinning, tree spatial arrangement (scattered or aligned with row spacing), and regeneration method—must be reported. Management of trees, crops, and livestock should cover pruning practices, residue handling, vegetation under trees, crop and soil management, fertilizer use, and grazing practices.

2.3.1. Individual isolated tree: Influence circles

Individual isolated trees can create influence zones, where variations in canopy size, root structure, and the quality and quantity of inputs to the soil lead to distinct soil environments and patterns centered around each tree (Sileshi and Nath, 2023). The commonly used 'influence circles' designs (Table 4) are illustrated in Figure 3. Whether a cross or a star design is selected, soil sampling distance should not be decided arbitrarily, it should be determined according to the Root Protection Area (RPA) of the individual tree. We recommend sampling at the end of the RPA and $\frac{1}{2}$ of the RPA from the tree as a minimum. For example, if the tree has a diameter at breast height (dbh) of 15 cm, the sampling points should be taken at 1.8 m and 0.9 m ($0.15 \text{ m} * 12 = 1.8 \text{ m}$).

Figure 3. Example of four directional sampling points located 1, 3, and 5 meters away from a tree trunk in the northern, eastern, southern, and western directions (A); STAR design (B) as used in some research papers.

2.3.2. Rows/transect of trees – alley cropping systems

A review on transect sampling for soil organic carbon monitoring in temperate alley cropping systems by Minarsch et al. (2024), identified different types of transects with different sample locations, composite sampling methods, and soil sampling depths (Figure 4). Very few studies (T3) have considered transect orientation bias, which considers the potential impact of differences in sun and wind exposure or soil runoff, which in turn can influence soil organic carbon accumulation.

Figure 4. Illustration of observed transect soil sampling methods. A) Frequency of transect types: T1) between two tree strips, T2) one side of the tree strip into the arable strip, and T3) both sides of the tree strip. B) Example sample locations: within both tree and arable strips (B1, B3, B4) or arable strip only (B2). C) Composite sampling approaches: one sample per transect (C1, C2) or multiple samples per transect, either from one or neighbouring transects (C4). D) Frequency of sampling across tree and arable strips and soil depths (0–100 cm+). Numbers indicate the number of identified transect designs out of 23 total.

For temperate Alley Cropping Systems (ACS), we recommend the methodology developed by Minarsch et al. (2024), consisting of transect sampling. The number of transects type and location should be dependent on the width of the alleys in the ACS. Sampling should be done in at least 4 replicate transects per ACS, positioned systematically, taking a minimum of 7 samples within each transect. These 7 sampling points are recommended to be positioned with their centre on the centre of the tree row Figure 5, sampling towards alleys on both side (on the tree row, 1m away, half the alley width away from the tree and one quarter of the alley width away from the tree).

Figure 5. Proposed transect soil sampling approach. A) Four transects, each with seven sample points at representative locations in the ACS: one in the tree strip and three in the arable strip on both sides, at 1 m, a quarter ($W/4$), and half ($W/2$) of the arable strip width. B) Tree strip sampling examples: B1) For wide tree spacing, sample points are near trees (c), between trees (a), and at a quarter distance (b and d). B2) For multiple tree rows, samples are taken in the strip center (b, c) and near edges (a, d). C) Composite sampling examples: C1) Each transect consists of four sub-transects around one key tree, with sub-samples combined for each location ($n = 7$). C2) Transects distributed across the ACS, with samples combined based on tree and arable strip areas ($n = 4$ per system).

Other studies suggest different sampling designs. Transects can be drafted between tree rows, with the spacing between sampling points depending on the row spacing. For example, Vaupel et al. (2025) used 0 (tree row), 1, 4, 8, 24 m from the tree rows in agrosilvopastoral alley cropping system (Figure 6A) while tree row, 5 m crop row when the distance between the two rows of trees is 10 m in synoptic alley-cropping system (Figure 6B), and open crop land (Figure 6C).

Figure 6. Transect sampling in different alley-cropping systems. **(A)** Vaupe et al. (2025) sampled at 0 (tree row), 1, 4, 8, and 24 meters from the tree rows in an agrosilvopastoral alley-cropping system. **(B)** Sampling at tree row and 5-meter crop row spacing with a 10-meter distance between tree rows in a synoptic alley-cropping system. **(C)** Open crop land without tree rows.

Table 4 presents a selection of publications that investigate the effects of isolated tree-based and tree-row agroforestry systems on various soil and environmental variables. The studies use different sampling designs to explore how tree presence influences factors such as soil chemistry, microbiome diversity, and crop yields. The distance between sampling points typically ranges from 2 to 5 meters, while some studies increase the sampling interval as the distance from the tree increases. This table summarizes the variables analysed, sampling designs, and provides links to the original sources for further reference.

Table 4. Example publications that use isolated tree-based and row/transect of trees studies with different sampling designs.

Source	Variable analysed	Location	Sampling design
Isolated tree-based			
Chandler and Chappell (2008)	Hydraulic conductivity under <i>Quercus robur</i>	England	1, 3, 5, 7, 9, 11 and 13 m from the trunk along eight transects radiating out along bearings of 0, 45, 90, 135, 180, 225, 270, 315, and 360 degrees
Moreno et al. (2007)	Total N under <i>Quercus ilex</i>	Spain	2, 5, 10, 15, and 20 m from the trunk
Montero et al. (2008)	Solar radiation under <i>Quercus ilex</i>	Spain	0.5, 1, 5, 10, 20 and 30 m from the trunk
Grouzis and Akpo (1997)	Herbaceous vegetation biomass under <i>Balanites</i> and <i>Acacia</i>	Senegal	1.25, 2.5, 3.75, 5.0, 6.25, 7.5, 8.75 and 10 m from the trunks in the four cardinal directions
Weltzin and Coughenour (1990)	Grass biomass under <i>Acacia tortilis</i>	Kenya	bole, 25, 50, 75, 100, 125, 150, 175 and 200% of the canopy radius
Tomlinson et al. (1998)	Root number, total N, available phosphorus (P) and potassium (K) under <i>Parkia biglobosa</i>	Burkina Faso	1, 3, 5, 7 and 9 m from the trunk
Belsky et al. (1989)	OC, available P, Ca, K, pH, soil moisture and temperature under <i>Acacia tortilis</i> and <i>Adansonia digitata</i>	Kenya	5 m intervals along the 50-m vegetation transects
Alemie (2009)	Light intensity, soil hydrophobicity; maize yield under <i>Eucalyptus</i>	Ethiopia	0.5, 1, 2, 5, 10, 15, 20 and 40 m distances from the tree
Yadav et al. (1993)	Mustard yield under <i>Acacia nilotica</i>	India	1, 3, 5, 7, 9, 11, 14, 18 and 22 m from the tree
(Singh et al. 1998)	Wheat yield under <i>Populus deltoides</i>	India	0.5, 1, 2, 3, 5 and 10 m under <i>Eucalyptus tereticornis</i>
Oliver et al. (2006)	Litter biomass, soil SOC and N under <i>Eucalyptus nova-anglica</i>	Australia	Star design at 16 distances from the tree every second metre along 30-m transects.
Schnabel et al. (2013)	SOC and N under <i>Quercus douglasii</i>	USA	11 equal distances from the tree bole using canopy radius (R) increments of 0.25 (0-2.5 x R)
Row/transect- based sampling design			
Vaupel et al. (2025)	Soil microbiome of a temperate agrosilvopastoral and syntropic agroforestry system	Germany	0, 1, 4, 8, 18 m from tree row; for 10 m wide strip, at 0 (tree row) and 5m (crop field)
Beule et al. (2020)	Temperate Agroforestry Croplands Promote Bacteria, Fungi, and Denitrification Genes in Soils	Germany	Tree row (1m from trunk), 1,7, and 24 m from the tree row
Minarsch et al. (2024)	review of transect sampling for soil organic carbon monitoring in temperate alley cropping systems -	Temperate region	0 (tree row), 3 sampling on arable land: 1 m, a quarter (W/4), and half (W/2) of the arable strip width on both sides of a strip. Total 7 samples.
Pardon et al. (2017)	Trees increase soil organic carbon and nutrient availability in temperate agroforestry systems	Belgium	- 2, 5, 10, 20 and 30 m away from the field edge - 2, 5 and 12 m from the closest tree row in alley cropping system

2.3.3. Area based sampling

Farm / Field scale

In farm/field-scale assessments, systematic pairwise sampling (Figure 7A) (e.g., Aynekulu et al. 2017; Syano et al. 2023) can be used, or alternatively, stratified random sampling can be applied within the treatment farm under agroforestry practices (Treatment) and the control farm under conventional land management (Figure 7B).

Figure 7. Sampling methods for farm/field-scale assessment. (A) Systematic pairwise sampling approach; (B) Stratified random sampling within the treatment farm under agroforestry practices (Treatment) and the control farm under conventional land management (Control)

Landscape scale

These designs—stratified random sampling, simple random sampling, and clustered random sampling (Figure 8)—offer different approaches to data collection based on study objectives and landscape variability. Stratified random sampling divides the area into distinct strata to ensure representation from each section, while simple random sampling selects points across the study area without any subdivision. Clustered random sampling, on the other hand, groups sampling points into clusters to focus on specific sub-areas, often optimizing fieldwork efficiency in larger regions.

Figure 8. Sampling methods: (a) Stratified random sampling, (b) Simple random sampling, (c) Clustered random sampling based on the Land Degradation Surveillance Framework ([LDSF](#)) which was developed by CIFOR-ICRAF and has been widely used in the global tropics.

Figure 9 provides an overview of the various agroforestry designs implemented across the eight living labs within the DigitAF project, highlighting the diversity of approaches in different European countries.

Figure 9. Different types of agroforestry designs in the eight living labs of the DigitAF project: (A) Silvopastoral system, isolated tree/area-based, Spain; (B) Row-based, Germany; (C) Grazed forest, area-based, Finland; (D) Row-based, Italy; (E) Row/area-based, Netherlands; (F) Row/area-based, UK; (G) Row/area-based, Czechia; (H) Area-based, Portugal.

2.4. Sample size determination and allocation

Sample size determination and allocation is a crucial process to ensure that field data is both representative and statistically reliable. This step addresses two key aspects:

- How many samples to take in the field: Determining the appropriate number of samples needed to capture variability.
- Where to take the samples: Identifying the precise locations within the field to maximize the accuracy and relevance of the results.

The steps we recommend for the sampling design process are described in Table 5, where we demonstrate the process using SOC as a representative example.

Table 5. Major steps in sampling design.

Step	Why	How
1. Define boundary of project area	Samples have to represent the area you are interested in, hence you need to define it exactly	On any map, draw the boundary of the area of interest (AOI). This is best done digitally. Google Earth is a suitable available tool
2. Define strata: Identify distinct regions of your project area that you anticipate will have different nutrient levels (if interested in stocks) and/or have different levels of change (if interested in SOC change). These define Strata	Sampling is most efficient if distinct areas are deliberately targeted, rather than leaving it to chance. If interested in specific interventions it makes sense to put more sampling effort into measuring them compared with the rest of the landscape.	Based on literature and local knowledge, select and map the boundaries of strata. Typically, 2-10 strata will be appropriate.
3. Choose a sample size	Taking too few samples leads to estimates with inadequate precision and is a waste of money. Taking too many samples generates more data than you need and is also a waste of money.	Decide how precise you want estimates to be. Use standard formulae to estimates of expected variation SOC to produce an initial sample size determination
4. Choose a sampling scheme	You need to decide how to allocate the samples size to difference strata and different levels of the hierarchy	Use the principles to produce a proposed design.
5. Estimate the cost of your sampling	You need to be sure the planned sampling is within budget before starting field work.	Estimate the cost as a combination of the fixed costs (e.g. equipment) plus variable costs (e.g. labour and travel), based on either your own information or experiences of others.
6. Reconcile cost and precision	If your initial design is too expensive you need to change something. Simply taking fewer samples is not an answer – you need to objectively change what you are aiming to get from the measurement.	Return to steps 1, 2, 4 or 5 and decided what to adjust, before recalculating the cost and precision
7. Generate the sample locations	You need exactly locations to visit for sampling. Random sampling (within strata and based on grids) is used to ensure that there are no biases.	Using standard code to generate random sample locations that conform to the strata and grids proposed. If samples end up in inappropriate locations (e.g., on a road, in water), generate a replacement. Output the list of sampling locations to your GPS.
8. Sampling for change in SOC	If you are selecting samples in order to measure change from a baseline or previous measurement, then you can usually improve on simply taking a second sample using these steps.	Choose the second or change detection sample to balance the strategies of (a) sampling the same locations to get precise estimate of change and (b) sampling new locations to 'fill gaps' in the first sample and hence get a good estimate of the stock at Time 2.

The number of plots required to estimate SOC stocks depends on the desired precision. Optimal size does not necessarily guarantee the desired precision of carbon estimate unless it is complemented with a proper unbiased sampling design. The number of plots required to measure carbon stocks is often within a precision level of $\pm 10\%$ of the mean SOC stocks at 95% confidence level (Boscolo et al., 2000). The number of samples needed for a given area can be calculated using the following equation (Pearson et al., 2005).

$$n = \frac{(N \times S)^2}{\frac{N^2 \times E^2}{t^2} + (N \times S^2)} \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

Where: n = number of plots

E = allowable error. Calculated by multiplying the mean carbon stocks by the desired precision (that is, mean carbon stock $\times 0.1$, for 10% precision)

t = the sample statistic from the t-distribution for the 95% confidence interval; t is usually set at 2 as sample size is unknown

N = number of sampling units in the population

S = standard deviation of stratum

Example. Taking the mean and standard deviation of SOC stocks of the five sentinel sites in western Kenya (see Section 8), the number of plots needed to report SOC stocks with a precision level of $\pm 10\%$ of the mean at 95% confidence level is calculated as follows.

Example

Taking the mean and standard deviation of SOC stocks of the five sentinel sites in western Kenya (see Section 8), the number of plots needed to report SOC stocks with a precision level of $\pm 10\%$ of the mean at 95% confidence level is calculated as follows.

Area of sentinel site	= 10,000 ha
Plot size	= 0.1 ha
Mean SOC stock	= 21.53 Mg C ha ⁻¹
Standard deviation	= 13.62
Precision	= 10%
N	= 10,000/0.1 = 100,000
E	= 21.53 \times 0.1 = 2.15
t	= 2

$$n = \frac{(100,000 \times 13.62)^2}{\frac{100,000^2 \times 2.15^2}{2^2} + (100,000 \times 13.62^2)}$$

= 160 plots

3. What to monitor in agroforestry systems

Soil health monitoring is crucial as it provides a standardized, consistent approach to assess the impact of agroforestry practices on soil quality, enabling informed decision-making and the development of effective policies based on robust, reliable data across diverse environmental conditions.

Table 6 outlines the key soil properties across various categories and highlights their roles in assessing soil health, which is essential for effective land management and sustainable agricultural practices. If resources allow, it would be beneficial to collect data on various tree-based features within the agroforestry system. Key measurements could include tree age, dominant woody species, tree height, crown diameter, trunk diameter (DBH), and tree density. These measurements will provide valuable insights into tree biomass carbon stocks, biodiversity, and the overall structural dynamics of the agroforestry system. Collecting such data can also help assess the system’s contribution to soil health and other ecosystem services, such as carbon sequestration for climate change mitigation.

Table 7 provides an overview of key tree attributes commonly assessed in agroforestry systems, along with the methods used to measure each parameter. These attributes offer valuable insights into tree growth, health, biodiversity, and the ecological impact of agroforestry practices, helping to evaluate their contribution to ecosystem services and sustainable land management.

Table 6. Key soil properties and their roles in soil health assessment.

Attributes	Property	Description
Physical	Soil bulk density	The mass per unit volume of the soil.
	Soil texture	The proportion of sand, silt, and clay affects water retention, drainage, and nutrient availability.
	Soil structure	The arrangement of soil particles into aggregates influences aeration, root growth, and water infiltration.
	Soil moisture	Monitoring moisture levels helps in managing irrigation and understanding drought conditions.
Chemical	Soil pH	Indicates the acidity or alkalinity of the soil, which affects nutrient availability and microbial activity.
	Nutrient content	Essential nutrients (N, P, K) and secondary/micronutrients need regular assessment to ensure optimal ranges.
	Organic matter	The amount of decomposed plant and animal material influences soil fertility and structure.
Biological	Microbial activity	The abundance and diversity of soil microorganisms affect nutrient cycling and organic matter decomposition.
	Soil respiration	Measures microbial activity and organic matter decomposition, indicating overall soil health.
Soil erosion and degradation	Erosion rates	Monitoring soil loss due to water or wind erosion helps in assessing the effectiveness of erosion control measures.
	Compaction	Assessing soil density and penetration resistance can identify issues with soil compaction that might hinder root growth and water infiltration.
	Salinity	
Soil contamination	Pollutants and toxins	Regular testing for heavy metals, pesticides, and other contaminants ensures soil safety and suitability for agriculture.

Table 7. Key vegetation properties and their roles in soil health assessment.

Attributes	Property	Description	How to measure
Tree and shrub	Age	Estimated age of the tree to assess its growth stage and productivity.	Estimate based on tree size, growth rate, and species-specific age-growth models. For known species, use historical planting records if available or ask those who planted them
	Tree species	Identification of the main tree species within the agroforestry system.	Visual identification of tree species using field guides or expert assistance.
	Tree height	The total height of the tree, reflecting its growth and canopy structure.	Measure with a clinometer for tall tree, tape measure/sticks for short trees.
	Crown diameter	The width of the tree's canopy, influencing shade, light interception, and microclimate.	Measure the widest diameter of the tree's crown using a tape measure. For irregular-shaped crowns, measure two perpendicular diameters and average them.
	Trunk diameter (DBH)	The diameter of the tree trunk at 1.3 meters above the ground, used to assess tree size and biomass.	Measure with a calliper or diameter tape at 1.3 meters above ground (DBH). If the tree has a branch or irregular shape, measure just below the first major branching.
	Tree density	The number of trees per unit area, indicating the level of tree cover and its ecological impact.	Count the number of trees within a specific plot (e.g., 1 ha) or use sampling methods such as quadrants or transects to estimate density.
	Tree health and condition	Observations of the tree's health, including any signs of disease or stress.	Visually inspect trees for signs of pests, diseases, wilting, discoloration, or abnormal growth. Record and categorize symptoms using a health scoring system if applicable.
Grass and herbs	Species	Identification of the grass and herb species present in the agroforestry system	Visual identification of species using field guides or expert assistance. Alternatively, use a plant identification key for accurate identification.
	Cover	The proportion of the ground covered by grass and herb species, indicating the density of vegetation cover.	Estimate the percentage of ground area covered by grass and herbs within a given plot. This can be done using a quadrat or a point-intercept method.
	Biomass	The total mass of living grass and herbaceous plants in each area.	Harvest a known area of grass and herb species (e.g., 1 m ² quadrat), dry the material, and weigh it to determine biomass.

3.1. Soil sampling

The DigitAF project aims to assess soil health in agroforestry systems by means of studying selected soil health indicators across the chemical (SOC and pH), physical (bulk density), and biological (earthworms) fractions of the soil, in accordance with Milestone 13 Methods for Carbon and Soil Health Assessments (den Herder et al., 2024). For harmonised reporting across DigitAF sites, the standard sampling depth for topsoil indicators is 0–20 cm. Where deeper soil information is required, additional subsoil layers may be collected and reported separately, but they should not be mixed with the 0–20 cm topsoil dataset.

In summary the process involves:

- Locating the predetermined sample location
- Taking composite soil samples using an auger from four sub plots in the plot.
- Measuring soil bulk density for the 0–20 cm topsoil layer, preferably using 0–10 cm and 10–20 cm increments, from the centre subplot.
- Collecting any associated data required (e.g. slope, topographic position, root depth restriction).
- Recording all data on prepared data collection forms or suitably programmed data capture devices (e.g. GPS).

The choice of 0–20 cm as the standard depth for topsoil in the LUCAS soil survey and related studies is supported by its widespread use in European soil research. The first LUCAS survey in 2009 collected nearly 20,000 topsoil samples at this depth across 25 EU countries (Orgiazzi et al., 2018), and subsequent studies, such as those by Ballabio et al. (2019), have developed maps of soil chemical properties at this same depth. Additionally, studies on soil organic carbon (SOC) change in Europe have consistently utilized the 0–20 cm depth, reinforcing its relevance for monitoring soil health and environmental changes (De Rosa et al., 2024). This depth is also aligned with the LDSF guidelines, which similarly use 0–20 cm as the topsoil layer for soil assessments. Using the 0–20 cm depth also ensures direct comparability with EU-wide baseline datasets and mapped soil indicators derived from LUCAS sampling, enabling consistent benchmarking across sites and countries (Orgiazzi et al. 2018; Ballabio et al. 2019; Orgiazzi et al. 2022). Therefore, all SOC, pH, bulk density and biological soil indicators reported as topsoil indicators in this guide should refer to the 0–20 cm layer, unless a different depth is explicitly stated and reported separately.

3.1.1. Soil sampling for SOC and pH

Setting up the sampling plot

Land Use and coverage Area frame Survey (LUCAS) approach

If you are using the LUCAS guidelines, a composite sampling strategy should be used. The sample collected at each location consists of five topsoil (0–20 cm) subsamples, which are mixed to form a single composite sample. If subsoil sampling is required, collect it as a separate sample layer and report it separately from the 0–20 cm topsoil sample. The first subsample is taken at the precise GPS coordinates of the pre-established LUCAS point, while the remaining four are taken 2 meters away from the central point, following the cardinal directions (North, East, South, and West) (Orgiazzi et al., 2018). Figure 10 illustrates the composite sampling strategy used to collect topsoil samples at a LUCAS point

(https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/ESDB_Archive/eusoils_docs/other/EUR26102EN.pdf).

Figure 10. Illustration of the composite sampling strategy used in the LUCAS guidelines. The first subsample is taken at the precise GIS coordinates of the pre-established LUCAS point (center of the plot). Four additional subsamples are collected 2 m away from the central point, following the cardinal directions (North, East, South, and West), to form a composite sample of topsoil (0–20 cm) (Orgiazzi et al., 2018). Bulk density data should be collected from the centre subplot for the same 0–20 cm topsoil layer, preferably using 0–10 cm and 10–20 cm increments.

Collecting top and sub-soil samples

Following the LUCAS approach, composite samples must be collected from five points. Vegetation residues, grass, and litter, if present, are removed from the surface before sampling and from the composite sample. Approximately 500 g of soil is air-dried before being transported to the laboratory for subsequent analysis. Labelling of the soil samples is critical and each soil sample label should contain information about the site, name, depth, and the date. For the standard DigitAF topsoil sample, the depth should be labelled as 0–20 cm. If additional subsoil samples are collected, they should be labelled with their own depth interval and analysed and reported separately. The label should be written on the outside of the bag as shown below and on a piece of cardboard placed inside the bag (Figure 11).

Figure 11. Photo of some of the soil samples collected.

3.1.2. Soil sampling for bulk density

Soil bulk density is the mass per unit volume of the soil. The soil volume includes solids and pores, which may contain air, water, or both. Bulk density reflects soil structure and depends on the proportion and quality of the mineral and organic soil components. Bulk density is usually expressed in Mg m^3 or the numerically equivalent g cm^{-3} (Cresswell and Hamilton, 2002). It is a soil property that typically has high spatial variability, and it is particularly sensitive to non-representativeness of the samples (e.g. presence of coarse fragments, cracks, roots). If possible, analyses should always be in triplicate for one sample (Blake and Hartge, 2018). As bulk density changes with water content, the water status of the soil at sampling must be specified (Blake and Hartge, 2018). Small errors in bulk density can lead to relatively high SOC stock variability.

According to LUCAS, bulk density is measured at 0–10 cm and 10–20 cm depths at the centre subplot, or at additional subplot locations if resources allow, following the LUCAS sampling scheme (Figure 10). Bulk density at each depth is determined by combining the air-dried weight and volume of the soil cores. The overall topsoil bulk density (0–20 cm) is the average of the 0–10 cm and 10–20 cm depths. Bulk density is included for two reasons: it is essential for calculating soil organic carbon stock, a key climate change indicator, and serves as an indicator of soil compaction, a major threat to soil quality.

The soil bulk density used in calculating SOC stocks should be measured for the same depth interval used for SOC concentration, in this guide the 0–20 cm topsoil layer. This is because the sampling of soils by coring almost invariably results in some compaction (Ellert et al., 2001). Thus, for example, the true depth of sampling when a 0–20 cm core is extracted almost always exceeds 20 cm and, therefore, the soil density in the core removed exceeds the actual field bulk density. This can lead to serious errors when later calculating soil carbon stock using bulk density and SOC concentration measured in independently taken samples. The most well-known, direct methods to determine soil bulk density are the undisturbed (intact) core method and the excavation method.

The undisturbed (intact) core method

The most common method of measuring soil bulk density is by collecting a known volume of soil using a metal ring pressed into the soil (intact core) and determining the weight after drying. This method works best for moist soils without coarse fragments. If the soil is too dry, it is possible to wet the soil manually to keep the core intact. To do this, a bottomless drum should be placed on the soil and filled with water, allowing the soil to wet naturally for 24 hours. Then, a horizontal surface should be prepared in the soil with a spade at the depth of sampling (Figure 12). For the standard topsoil assessment, cores should be collected from 0–10 cm and 10–20 cm, or from a single 0–20 cm core where the equipment allows accurate sampling without compaction. A steel ring is pushed or gently hammered into the soil. A block of wood may be used to protect the ring. Avoid pushing the ring in too far or the soil will compact. Excavate around the ring without disturbing or loosening the soil it contains and carefully remove it with the soil intact. Remove any excess soil from the outside of the ring and cut any plants or roots off at the soil surface with scissors. Pour the soil into the plastic bag and seal the bag. Common sources of error when measuring bulk density are: disrupting the soil while sampling, inaccurate trimming, and inaccurate measuring of the volume of the ring.

The appropriate core sample size (volume) depends on soil bulk density, as well as the size and characteristics of the coarse fraction. As a result, standardizing the sample size can be challenging. For soils composed primarily of fine earth, sample sizes of 100 cm^3 are commonly used to determine bulk

density. However, smaller samples may underrepresent coarse fragments, leading to an underestimation of bulk density in gravelly soils.

Figure 12. Steel cylinder core sampling for bulk density. (A) The cylinder is hammered into the soil from the surface using a mallet and a piece of wood to cushion the mallet strikes. (B) The soil cylinder is recovered from the soil, and excess soil is trimmed off along the lower edge of the cylinder using a knife. (C) After the top layers are sampled, a horizontal surface is established for sampling the next deeper layer. (D) The cylinder is pushed into the soil until it is flush with the surface of the layer.

Excavation method

This method has been found useful for loose soils, especially surface soils, when it is impossible to collect an intact soil sample applying the undisturbed core method, or for soils with abundant coarse fragments. Bulk density is determined by excavating a quantity of soil, drying and weighing it, and determining the volume of the excavation by filling the hole with sand of known volume per unit mass or water (Grossman and Reinsch, 2002). A special apparatus called sand-funnel can be used. After levelling the soil surface, a hole should be excavated using the template of the apparatus. The size of the hole will depend on the apparatus, but a larger (approximately 12 cm in diameter) hole will likely result in smaller error in bulk density estimation. The depth of the hole will depend on the depth of the evaluated layer. All the excavated soil should be retained in a container to determine its dry weight as described in the undisturbed core method.

The volume of the hole should be determined by filling it up with clean, dry, free-flowing sand (standard sand with uniform particle-size 0.841-0.25 mm is recommended). The level of the sand should be adjusted to the level of the bottom of the template. An error of 1 mm in adjusting the sand level may result in an error of 0.01 in the bulk density. Using a funnel placed on the template to avoid this error is highly desirable. To estimate the soil volume a mass-to-volume ratio is used. For this reason, the mass-to-volume ratio of the sand must be pre-calibrated by letting the sand fall from a similar height and at a similar rate of flow as in the procedure of measuring bulk density.

$$\text{Soil sample volume (cm}^3\text{)} = \text{Mass of the sand (g)} / \text{Density of the sand (g cm}^{-3}\text{)} \quad (\text{Eq. 2})$$

Indirect methods of determining bulk density may be useful after suitable calibration. Among those are radiation methods, for example gamma radiation transmission or scattering techniques, requiring special equipment (gamma source and detector), and pedotransfer functions (PTFs).

Soil bulk density should be determined in the same core in which SOC concentration is measured. For estimating bulk density, direct measurement methods should be used, specifically the undisturbed (intact) core method and the excavation method, because these can provide the most accurate determination of bulk density. The clod method should not be used because for SOC stock measurements the bulk density of soil layers or horizons must be represented.

3.1.3. Soil sampling for earthworm abundance

Earthworms play a crucial role in ecosystem functioning, and their diversity can serve as an indicator of ecosystem health. In this study, we will analyze soil samples to assess the diversity and abundance of earthworms. If resources allow, it is also important to examine soils for bacteria and Arbuscular Mycorrhizal Fungi (AMF) to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the soil's microbial and faunal composition of the soil. Phillips et al. (2019) compiled a global dataset of sampled earthworm communities from 9212 sites in 57 countries as a basis for predicting patterns in earthworm diversity, abundance, and biomass.

- Earthworm abundance: earthworm will represent the soil macro fauna. Earthworm sampling should follow internationally recognised methods where feasible. The reference standard is ISO 23611-1:2018, based on excavation of a 50 cm × 50 cm × 20 cm soil monolith followed by hand-sorting (with optional extraction), and reporting abundance as individuals m⁻². Physical hand counting is a widely used method for measuring earthworm abundance in soil studies (Bartlett et al. 2010). Full monoliths (50 × 50 × 20 cm) to be excavated to a depth of 20 cm. The excavated soil from the monoliths needs to be hand sorted for soil macrofauna, mainly earthworm, which are preserved in 75% alcohol and fixed in 4% formaldehyde. After that, they will be transported in sealed vials to the laboratory for enumeration and biomass determination. If collecting soil monoliths is difficult to execute, earthworms can be counted at the field level. If monoliths are taken, we will count the number of earthworms and determine their biomass in the laboratory.
- Sampling should be done at times of the year when the earthworms are not forced by environmental conditions (i.e. low soil moisture and/or high temperatures), with winter and midsummer periods being unfavourable in temperate regions (ISO 2018). Where site conditions, labour/time, farmer constraints, or soil stoniness make the ISO monolith impractical, earthworms may be assessed using smaller monoliths commonly applied in peer-reviewed studies, for example 25 cm × 25 cm × 20 cm, 20 cm × 20 cm × 20 cm, or 25 cm × 25

cm × 30 cm, provided the chosen approach is applied consistently within a Living Lab and fully documented.

- Different studies use different dimensions of soil volume to assess earthworms. For example, Mulia et al. (2021) used a 50 x 50 x 30 cm sample plot to assess earthworms Figure 13. A study in European soils was conducted to excavate a 50 cm x 50 cm x 25 cm deep soil block (https://literatur.thuenen.de/digbib_extern/dn062669.pdf). Since this study could complement the LUCAS soil biodiversity dataset (Orgiazzi et al., 2022), we suggest using a 20 cm soil depth. LUCAS followed the primer pairs developed by (BIENERT et al., 2012), designed based on the mitochondrial DNA method they introduced.
- For harmonisation across DigitAF Living Labs and to support consistency in field implementation, the default earthworm sampling unit in this guide is a soil monolith of 20 × 20 × 20 cm, collected by hand sorting and reported as individuals m⁻² (ISO 2018). Other monolith sizes used in the literature (e.g., 25 × 25 × 20 cm; 25 × 25 × 30 cm; 50 × 50 × 20 cm) may be applied where site conditions or partner protocols require, but the selected size must be used consistently across all sites and sampling rounds, and clearly reported.

To strengthen comparability across Living Labs, teams should record (i) monolith dimensions (area and depth), (ii) sampling date/season and soil moisture status, (iii) extraction approach (hand-sorting only vs. hand-sorting plus expellant), (iv) number of replicate pits per site, and (v) how abundance was standardised to individuals m⁻².

Step-by-step process for earthworm sampling

Prepare sampling equipment

- Gather necessary tools for earthworm collection, such as a soil corer or spade, to excavate the soil.
- Ensure all equipment is clean and sanitized to avoid contamination or disturbance of the sample.

Select sampling locations

- Use the sample sampling points soil sampling soil chemical and physical properties

Excavate soil samples

- At each sampling point, use the corer or spade to dig a soil block of the desired size (default: 20 cm x 20 cm x 20 cm deep) Figure 13
- Carefully remove the soil to minimize disruption to the earthworms' natural position in the soil profile.

Collect earthworms

- Gently hand-count the earthworms from the excavated soil, separating them by species if possible.
- Record the number and type of earthworms in each sample.

Store samples properly

- If necessary, place collected earthworms in a temporary holding container with moist soil until further analysis can be done.
- Ensure they are kept under conditions like their natural habitat to avoid stress.

Report data:

- Report earthworm abundance data as number of individuals per m²

Figure 13. 50 x 50 x 30 cm sample plot to assess earthworms

Equipment

You will need the following:

- A spade (to dig the pits)
- Five plastic tubes of 80% ethanol (to store and preserve earthworms)
- A sorting tray (to place the soil on to sort through and look for earthworms, alternatives include pots or bin bags)
- Labels and alcohol resistant pen/pencil (to label your samples and ensure they do not get mixed up)
- Notebook and map (to make note of the location, habitat and other important factors)
- Pointed non-serrated forceps (optional but useful)
- Gloves (to keep your hands clean)

Table 8 summarizes the earthworm sampling methods, sampling area dimensions, **and** soil depths used in various studies. For DigitAF harmonisation, the default (“recommended”) monolith is 20 × 20 × 20 cm (hand sorting), with alternative monolith sizes listed for cases where partner protocols or field constraints require them, provided the chosen size is applied consistently and clearly reported. The table provides an overview of the different techniques employed for earthworm sampling, such as hand sorting, pitfall traps, and soil-core extraction. It also details the dimensions of the sampling areas (in centimetres) and the corresponding soil depths, which vary across different research studies. This information can serve as a useful reference for comparing methodologies and understanding the sampling protocols in agroforestry and ecological research. Table 8 summarises common earthworm monolith dimensions used in the literature, however DigitAF uses the default monolith size specified above for harmonisation.

Based on these studies, commonly used soil block dimensions include 25 × 25 × 30 cm and larger monoliths (e.g., 50 × 50 × 20–30 cm). For DigitAF, the default sampling unit is 20 × 20 × 20 cm for harmonisation across Living Labs, while other monolith sizes may be used as alternatives only when required by partner protocols or field constraints, provided the selected size is applied consistently across all sites and sampling rounds, and clearly reported.

Table 8. Summary of earthworm sampling methods, sampling pit dimensions in various studies.

Study	Soil volume/monolith (area and depth)	Sampling Method	Remark
ISO 2018	50 cm × 50 cm × 20 cm	Hand sorting	ISO 23611-1:2018 Soil quality — Sampling of soil invertebrates Part 1: Hand-sorting and extraction of earthworms
Cardinael et al. (2019)	25 cm × 25 cm × 20 cm	Hand sorting Chemical	Earthworms were collected at each site during their maximum biological activity in March/April in France
UK Centre for Ecology & Hydrology	20 cm x 20 cm x 20 cm	Hand sorting	UK
Anderson and Ingram (1993)	25 cm x 25 cm x 30 cm		Tropical Soil Biology and Fertility: A Handbook of Methods
CIFOR-ICRAF	25 cm x 25 cm x 30 cm	Hand sorting	METHOD FOR SAMPLING AND ISOLATION OF SOIL MACROFAUNA
Bignell et al. (2008)	50 cm x 50 cm x 20 cm 25 cm x 25 cm x 30 cm		A Handbook of Tropical Soil Biology: Sampling and Characterization of Below-Ground Biodiversity
FiBL Europe	30 cm x 30 cm x 30 cm	Hand sorting Chemical	FiBL Switzerland, FiBL Germany, FiBL Austria, FiBL France
Soildiver	25 cm x 25 cm x 25 cm		
FAO	20 cm x 20 cm x 25 cm	Manual extraction and sorting	Structure and ecology of soil macrofauna communities
The Earthworm Society of Britain	25 cm x 25 cm x 10 cm	Hand sorting	
De Wandeler et al. (2016)	25 cm x 25 cm x 20 cm	Hand sorting	Drivers of earthworm incidence and abundance across European forests
Pelosi et al. (2009)	40 cm x 40 cm x 30 cm	Hand sorting	France
Rutgers et al. (2016)	Netherlands: 20 cm x 20 cm x 20 cm Ireland: 25 cm x 25 cm x 25 cm Scotland: 50 cm x 50 cm x 10 cm France: 25 cm x 25 cm x 25 cm Spain: 50 cm x 100 cm x 20 cm Slovenia: 50 cm x 50 cm x 50 cm Denmark: 25 cm x 25 cm x 30 cm and 50 cm x 50 cm x 30 cm	Hand sorting Chemical	Mapping earthworm communities in Europe
Liu et al. (2025)	50 cm x 50 cm x 10 cm	hand-sorting and mustard extraction	Grasslands support more diverse and resilient earthworm communities to climate change than croplands in Central Europe

Singh et al. (2016) evaluated various earthworm sampling methods, highlighting the advantages, disadvantages, and efficiency of each method. These methods include hand sorting, the octet method, formalin extraction, mustard extraction, allyl isothiocyanate (AITC), and the onion extraction method (Table 9).

Table 9. Summary of earthworm sampling methods, sampling pit dimensions in various studies.

Method	Description	Advantages	Disadvantages	Efficiency
Hand Sorting	Manual extraction by sorting through the soil.	Effective for earthworms > 0.2 g and recovering cocoons.	Time-consuming and labor-intensive.	Less efficient than chemical methods but effective for larger earthworms.
Octet Method	Extracts <i>anecic</i> species, used when chemical methods are not viable.	Effective for deep-burrowing <i>anecic</i> species.	Not effective for surface-dwelling worms.	Efficient for <i>anecic</i> species.
Formalin Method	Chemical extraction using formalin.	Highly efficient (20–60 times more efficient than hand sorting).	Toxic and may not be suitable for all environments.	Very high efficiency, but toxic to both earthworms and the environment.
Mustard Extraction	Uses mustard solution to extract earthworms.	Simple, low-cost, and effective for deep-burrowing species.	Limited to certain species, may not work for surface worms.	Highly efficient for deep-burrowing species.
Allyl Isothiocyanate (AITC)	Uses AITC chemical solution to extract earthworms.	Simple, low-cost, efficient for deep-burrowing species.	Chemical method, may not be suitable for all species.	Highly efficient for deep-burrowing species.
Onion Extraction	Non-toxic onion solution for extraction.	Inexpensive, non-toxic, and environmentally friendly.	May be less efficient than formalin or mustard.	Low-cost and non-toxic, efficient for deep-burrowing species, but less effective than formalin.

3.1.4. Soil sampling for bacteria and fungi

We will use the soil samples collected for chemical and physical properties to quantify bacteria, fungi, and arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi (AMF) when resources allow, counting the colony forming units for bacteria and fungi. Compound microscopes are recommended to count AMF spores.

Several studies have reported that a higher fungal-to-bacterial (F:B) ratio is a good indicator of healthy soil (Birhane et al., 2020). This is partly because higher F:B ratios are linked to greater carbon storage potential (Malik et al., 2016). It is recommended to obtain the F:B ratio when resources allow.

4. Laboratory analyses

Two types of data sets will come to the lab from the field:

1. Composite soil samples and
2. Bulk density or cumulative mass soil samples

The composite samples are used to determine soil carbon concentration (g C kg^{-1}) while the cumulative mass soil samples are used to calculate the SOC stocks (kg C m^{-2}). The soil processing procedures are described in the standard operating procedures ([view pdf](#)) for soil processing and are only summarized in Table 10.

Table 10. Procedures in soil sample processing and laboratory analyses.

Steps	Composite soil samples	Cumulative mass soil samples
Air-dry the soils samples	Spread your sample out as a thin layer into a shallow tray. Drying can be done in large room, a custom-made solar dryer, or a forced-air oven at 40 °C. Break up clods as far as possible to aid drying. It is important to ensure that no material from a sample is lost or discarded as weights of soil fractions are to be recorded on processing. Contamination from dust, plaster or other potential contaminants should be avoided.	Spread your sample out as a thin layer into a shallow tray. Drying can be done in large room, a custom-made solar dryer, or a forced-air oven at 40 °C. Break up clods as far as possible to aid drying. It is important to ensure that no material from a sample is lost or discarded as weights of soil fractions are to be recorded on processing.
Weigh and sieve	Weigh the whole dried soil sample to 0.1 g using a calibrated top-pan balance and record the weight. Sieve the soil with 2 mm mesh size sieve and weigh the coarse fragments (> 2 mm).	Weigh the whole dried soil sample to 0.1 g using a calibrated top-pan balance and record the weight. Sieve the soil with 2 mm mesh size sieve and weigh the coarse fragments (> 2 mm).
Sub-sample	Sub-sample a fine soil fraction and send to a lab for carbon concentration analysis. Store adequate fine soil sample (~ 750 kg) in case further analyses are required later.	Determine gravimetric moisture content on a subsample
Measure soil organic carbon concentration	Measure soil organic carbon concentration in a soil lab. When sample is size reasonably large, infrared spectral measurement is a cheaper and rapid alternative method to the conventional method. In this case you will analyze a subset of the soils samples (~10%) using conventional laboratory procedures to calibrate and validate the infrared spectral measurements.	Calculate soil mass per unit volume of soil. Determine volume of soil using auger diameter and auguring depth.

4.1. Soil organic carbon

Total carbon and organic carbon concentration (g C kg^{-1}) are determined on soil reference samples only, by thermal oxidation (Skjemstad and Baldock, 2008) using a carbon analyzer according to Standard ISO 10694: Soil quality - Determination of organic and total carbon after dry combustion (elementary analysis). These reference soil carbon measurements are calibrated to soil infrared spectral measurements and the calibrations then used to predict carbon values for all samples. Soil reference carbon is determined on total and acidified samples, i.e. fumigated with hydrochloric acid to remove inorganic carbon (Harris, Horwáth and van Kessel, 2001). Inorganic carbon is estimated as the difference between unacidified and acidified carbon. Infrared spectroscopy offers promise for a rapid, reliable and cost-effective measurement of soil organic carbon (Winowiecki et al., 2016).

4.2. Soil pH

According to LUCAS, soil pH is measured following the ISO 10390:1994 standard (ISO, 1994a). The method includes the determination of pH in both water and calcium chloride (Orgiazzi et al., 2018).

4.3. Coarse fragments

In all samples, macroscopic roots and all particles, mineral and organic, with a diameter larger than 2 mm, are removed by dry sieving. The mineral particles not passing the 2-mm sieve are weighed separately to determine the content of coarse fragments. Sampling adequate soil volumes is critical to accurately estimate soil coarse fragment content, as demonstrated by the study's comparison of cross-section and particle size analysis methods (Buchter et al., 1994).

4.4. Summary

Table 11 summarizes various methods used to measure key soil health indicators, including soil organic carbon (SOC), bulk density, soil pH, and earthworm diversity. It highlights the advantages and disadvantages of each method, helping to guide the selection of appropriate techniques based on study requirements, available resources, and the level of precision needed.

Table 11. Table soil health indicators: methods, pros, and cons.

Soil parameter	Method of measurement	Pros	Cons
Soil Organic Carbon (SOC)	Dry Combustion (Elemental Analyzer)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - High accuracy and precision - Reliable and widely accepted - Provides direct and precise quantification 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Expensive and requires specialized equipment - Destructive (consumes soil samples) - Labor-intensive sample preparation (drying and grinding)
	Loss on Ignition (LOI)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cost-effective and simple - Ideal for bulk analysis and large sample sizes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Less accurate, especially in soils with high clay content - Can overestimate SOC due to interference from non-organic materials
	Walkley-Black (Wet Oxidation)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Used on some farm soils - Inexpensive and easy to perform 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Less accurate for soils with high clay, iron, or aluminium content - Potential overestimation of SOC
	Mid-Infrared Spectroscopy (MIR)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Non-destructive, fast, repeatable, and suitable for high throughput analysis 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Requires calibration and can be influenced by soil texture, moisture content, and mineral interference
Bulk density	Sample Ring	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reliable for shallow depths - Simple and widely accepted 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Disturbs soil, especially for deep sampling - Time and labour-intensive, particularly for deep sampling
	Auger with Sampling Plate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Suitable for deep sampling with low soil disturbance - Quick deployment and ideal for spatially variable environments - Efficient for large-scale sampling campaigns 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Potential contamination and sample variability - Struggles with compact or rocky soils
Soil pH	pH Meter	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Quick and easy measurement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sensitive to soil moisture and texture, requiring calibration for

		- Provides accurate and reproducible results	different soil types - Potential contamination from the sample container or soil residues
	Soil Suspension (1:1 or 1:2)	- Commonly used and simple method for field and lab studies - Provides reliable readings for range of soil types	- Requires proper soil suspension preparation for consistency - Can be affected by salt content in soil or moisture conditions
Earthworms	Hand-Sorting	Direct, manual observation - Provides species-level identification	- Labor-intensive, particularly for large soil areas - Potentially disturbed by sampling
	Soil sashing	Effective for capturing earthworms and other macrofauna in soil	- Time-consuming and may lead to loss of small organisms
	DNA metabarcoding	- Non-destructive, allows for identification of species from soil samples - Can be used for high-throughput analyses of earthworm diversity	- Requires specialized equipment and analysis Potential contamination and costly for large-scale studies

5. Data analysis and reporting

By the end of the lab work you should have an estimate of soil organic carbon (SOC) stock as kg per m² for the standard 0–20 cm topsoil layer, with bulk density, coarse fragments, soil depth and uncertainty reported transparently for each field sample location. The statistical methods needed depend mainly on the products you are aiming for. The aims of data analysis are then to:

1. Turn this raw data into the information products you set out to generate.
2. Spot any other patterns that could be important.

Principles of data analysis

Four principles of data analysis should be followed in all work. These are not specific to estimation of SOC, but your data analysis will not go well if they are ignored.

1. Focus on meeting the output objectives but be alert for unanticipated results that might be important.
2. Every estimated quantity that you produce should have a measure of precision (e.g. standard error or confidence interval) attached to it.
3. Methods used should be repeatable and objective and not based on arbitrary decisions. However, only the simplest methods can be fully automated.
4. Keep records of all the data and code used along with details of analysis decisions, so that analysis can be repeated or updated at any time.

5.1. Calculation of SOC stocks

SOC stocks in this guide should be calculated and reported for the standard 0–20 cm topsoil layer. Where comparisons across treatments or time are likely to be affected by changes in bulk density, the equivalent soil mass approach can be used as an additional analysis, but the reporting depth and assumptions must be stated clearly.

To express changes in soil carbon stocks accurately, bulk density must be measured for the same depth interval used for SOC concentration. Estimates of soil carbon stocks to a fixed depth using single depth

bulk density are mostly biased due to the spatial and temporal variability in bulk density (Lee et al., 2009). Despite the high carbon concentration in the topsoil, the 0–20 cm layer may have lower soil mass than deeper layers because bulk density is often lower near the surface. The variability in bulk density with depth can be addressed by establishing relationship between cumulative soil mass and volume. It is likely that projects designed to enhance soil organic carbon (e.g. afforestation) will also cause the soil bulk density to decrease. Management that decreases bulk density can lead to underestimation of SOC stocks when fixed-depth calculations are used without accounting for soil mass, while management that increases bulk density can have the opposite effect (Ellert and Bettany, 1995; Gifford and Roderick, 2003).

If it is expected that the soil bulk density will change significantly during the course of the project (Figure 14), it is recommended to assess the impact of expressing the changes in soil carbon on an equivalent soil mass basis on the total projected change in soil carbon stocks (Dupla et al., 2024). This should be presented as a complementary analysis to the standard 0–20 cm fixed-depth estimate, not as a replacement, unless the study design explicitly uses equivalent soil mass from the beginning.

Figure 14. Illustration of the importance of sampling at equivalent soil mass (ESM) to avoid flawed SOC stock estimates associated with bulk density changes (here due to recent tillage).

To consider possible changes in bulk density over time or due to management, comparisons of SOC stocks shall be made on an equivalent soil mass basis (ESM). Samples from at least three discrete, contiguous and successive soil layers should be available to describe how bulk density and SOC concentrations change from the surface layer downward. When using ESM for repeated SOC measurements or point-in-time comparisons, estimates shall be made for the same point (i.e. spatial and depth) or area over time. For sampling schemes where individual samples are taken, these should be aggregated to ensure they represent the same point or area. The method for calculating ESM shall remain consistent across all sampling times.

Using the bulk density of the whole soil:

$$SOC_i \text{ stock} = OC_i \times BDi \times (1 - gGi) \times ti \times 0.1 \quad (\text{Eq. 3})$$

where,

SOC_i (Mg C ha⁻¹) is the soil organic carbon stock of depth increment i

OC_i (mg C g⁻¹ fine earth) is the organic carbon content of the fine earth fraction

(< 2 mm) of the depth increment i

BD_i (g soil cm⁻³ soil) is the mass of soil per total volume of the soil sample of the depth increment i

gG_i (g coarse fragment g⁻¹soil) is the mass fraction of coarse mineral fragment, thus

gGi is the mass fraction fine earth (g fine earth g⁻¹ soil) of the depth increment i

t_i is the thickness (depth, in cm) of the depth increment i

0.1 is a factor for converting mg C cm⁻² to Mg C ha⁻¹

Using the bulk density of the fine earth (BDfine1), as in IPCC (2003, p. 90)

$$SOC_i \text{ stock} = OC_i \times BD_{fine1i} \times (1 - vG_i) \times t_i \times 0.1 \quad (\text{Eq.4})$$

where,

SOC_i (Mg C ha⁻¹) is the soil organic carbon stock of depth increment i

OC_i (mg C g⁻¹ fine earth) is the organic carbon content of the fine earth fraction (< 2 mm) in the depth increment i

BD_{fine1i} (g fine earth cm⁻³ fine earth) is the mass of fine earth per volume of fine earth = (dry soil mass [g] – coarse fragment mass [g]) / (soil sample volume [cm³] – coarse fragment volume [cm³]) in the depth increment i

volume fraction fine earth (cm³ fine earth cm⁻³ soil) = 1 – volume fraction coarse fragment [cm³ coarse fragment cm⁻³ soil]

t is the thickness (depth, in cm) of the depth increment i

0.1 is a factor for converting mg C cm⁻² to Mg C ha⁻¹

5.2. Reporting SOC stocks

Mean and standard error for a stratum

$$\bar{Y} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n y_i \quad (\text{Eq. 5})$$

where \bar{Y} denotes mean carbon stock (t ha⁻¹), n denotes the sample size and y_i denotes the value measured at the i -th sampling location (plot).

$$\bar{V} = \frac{1}{n(n-1)} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{Y})^2 \quad (\text{Eq. 6})$$

where \bar{V} denotes sampling variance, n denotes sample size, $\bar{V}y_i$ denotes the value measured at the i -th sampling location (plot) and \bar{Y} denotes mean carbon stock (t ha⁻¹).

$$SE = \sqrt{\bar{V}} \quad (\text{Eq. 7})$$

where SE denotes standard error and \bar{V} denotes sampling variance.

Mean and standard error for strata

$$\bar{Y} = \frac{\sum_{h=1}^L N_h \times \bar{Y}_h}{N} \quad (\text{Eq. 8})$$

where \bar{Y} denotes mean SOC stock (t ha⁻¹), N_h denotes size of stratum h (ha), \bar{Y}_h denotes mean SOC stock of stratum h (t ha⁻¹) and N denotes size of the entire study area (ha).

$$SE = \sqrt{\sum_{h=1}^L \left(\frac{N_h}{N}\right)^2 \times \frac{S_h^2}{n_h}} \quad (\text{Eq. 9})$$

where SE denotes standard error, N_h denotes size of stratum h , S_h^2 variance of stratum h

Confidence interval of the mean

$$\bar{Y}_{SI} \pm t_{1-\alpha/2} \times \sqrt{\bar{V}} \quad (\text{Eq. 10})$$

where $t_{1-\alpha/2}$ is the quantile of the student distribution with $(n-1)$ degree of freedom. $(1-\alpha/2)$

Monitoring changes in SOC stocks over time is essential for understanding how different land management practices and environmental conditions influence soil carbon dynamics.

Table 12. and Table 13 provides an example of data on the changes in SOC stocks measured at different time intervals, highlighting the variability in SOC levels under specific conditions.

Table 12. Example data on changes in SOC stocks between time measurements.

Land use	Plot	SOC stocks (t ha ⁻¹)		
		T ₀ (baseline)	T ₁ (after 5 years)	Change (T ₁ - T ₀)
Crop land (252 ha)	1	35	36	1
	2	22	24	2
	3	33	32	-1
	4	25	26	1
	5	19	22	3
	6	27	30	3
Forest land (197.9 ha)	1	35	38	3
	2	22	21	-1
	3	33	33	0
	4	25	27	2
	5	19	19	0
Grazing land (214 ha)	1	35	37	2
	2	22	26	4
	3	33	34	1
	4	25	26	1
	5	19	21	2

Table 13. Summary data on changes in SOC stocks between time measurements.

Summary		T ₀ (baseline)	T ₁ (after 5 years)	Change (T ₁ - T ₀)
Mean SOC	t ha ⁻¹	26.81	28.25	1.44
Standard deviation SOC	t ha ⁻¹	6.21	6.16	1.46
Standard error of mean	t ha ⁻¹	1.55	1.54	0.37
t value ($\alpha = 0.05$, n-1)		2.13	2.13	2.13
95% confidence level of the mean		3.30	3.28	0.79
95% CI of mean, lower	t ha ⁻¹	23.51	24.97	0.65
95% CI of mean, upper	t ha ⁻¹	30.11	31.53	2.23
Total SOC stocks	t	17815	18772	957
95% confidence level of total SOC	t	2194	2180	525
95% CI of total, lower	t	15621	16593	432
95% CI of total, upper	t	20009	20952	1482
CO ₂ e total	t	65323	68831	3509
95% confidence level of total CO ₂ e	t	8044	7992	1925

CO ₂ e CI total, lower	T	57279	60840	1584
CO ₂ e CI total, upper	t	73367	76823	5433

Report				
Mean SOC ± 95% confidence level	t ha ⁻¹	26.81 ± 3.3015	28.25 ± 3.28	1.44 ± 0.79
Total SOC ± 95% confidence level	t	17815 ± 2194	18772 ± 2180	957 ± 525
Total CO ₂ equivalent	CO ₂ e	65323 ± 8044	68831 ± 7992	3509 ± 1925

5.3. Presentation and use of the results

Presenting the results is straightforward. The estimates and maps can be presented in obvious ways. They should always be accompanied by estimates of error. They should also be accompanied by a detailed description of the methods used, for example by reference to this protocol. Note that every part of the process needs to be described, not just the statistical, sampling or lab procedures. It is good practice to lodge all data from the exercise in a public archive. This allows the project keep data secure for follow up and allows others to make use of it for further analyses and to link it with other data.

- Within each land use category designated as key, to assess which subcategories are significant; and
- Use the results of this analysis to determine what categories and subcategories should be prioritized in terms of methodological choice.

Units

CO₂ emissions/removals and emissions of non-CO₂ gases are reported in gigagrams (Gg). To convert tonnes C to Gg CO₂, multiply the value by 44/12 and 10⁻³.

6. Glossary

Most of the definitions were taken from The Cambridge Dictionary of Statistics (Everitt, 2002).

Bias: in general terms, deviation of results or inferences from the truth, or processes leading to such deviation. More specifically, the extent to which the statistical method used in a study does not estimate the quantity thought to be estimated or does not test the hypothesis to be tested.

Clustered data: a term applied to both data in which the sampling units are grouped into clusters sharing some common feature, for example, animal litters, families or geo- graphical regions, and longitudinal data in which a cluster is defined by a set of repeated measures on the same unit. A distinguishing feature of such data is that they tend to exhibit intracluster correlation, and their analysis needs to address this correlation to reach valid conclusions.

Confidence interval: a range of values, calculated from the sample observations, that is believed, with a particular probability, to contain the true parameter value. A 95% confidence interval, for example, implies that were the estimation process repeated and again, then 95% of the calculated intervals would be expected to contain the true parameter value. Note that the stated probability level refers to properties of the interval and not to the parameter itself which is not considered a random variable.

Hierarchical/nested sampling: a design in which levels of one or more factors are subsampled within one or more other factors so that, for example, each level of a factor B occurs at only one level of another factor A. Factor B is said to be nested within factor A. An example might be where interest centres on assessing the effect of hospital and doctor on a response variable, patient satisfaction.

Measurement error: errors in reading, calculating or recording a numerical value. The difference between observed values of a variable recorded under similar conditions and some fixed true value.

Random sampling: either a set of n independent and identically distributed random variables, or a sample of n individuals selected from a population in such a way that each sample of the same size is equally likely.

Sample: a selected subset of a population chosen by some process usually with the objective of investigating properties of the parent population.

Sample size: the number of individuals to be included in an investigation. Usually chosen so that the study has a particular power of detecting an effect of a particular size.

Sampling: the process of selecting some part of a population to observe to estimate something of interest about the whole population. To estimate the amount of recoverable oil in a region, for example, a few sample holes might be drilled, or to estimate the abundance of a rare and endangered bird species, the abundance of birds in the population might be estimated on the pattern of detections from a sample of sites in the study region. Some obvious questions are how to obtain the sample and make the observations and, once the sample data are to hand, how best to use them to estimate the characteristic of the whole population.

Sampling design: the procedure by which a sample of units is selected from the population.

Sampling error: the difference between the sample result and the population characteristic being estimated. In practice, the sampling error can rarely be determined because the population characteristic is not usually known. With appropriate sampling procedures, however, it can be kept small, and the investigator can determine its probable limits of magnitude. SOC (soil organic carbon) stock vs concentration.

Sampling frames: the portion of the population from which the sample is selected. They are usually defined by geographic listings, maps, directories, membership lists or from telephone or other electronic formats.

Soil infrared spectroscopy: spectroscopy is the study of the interaction between matter and radiated energy¹. Soil Infrared spectroscopy (IR spectroscopy) uses infrared region of the electromagnetic spectrum that is light with a longer wavelength and lower frequency than visible light to estimate soil properties like soil organic carbon content. IR is an established technology for rapid, non-destructive characterization of the composition of materials based on the interaction of electromagnetic energy with matter^{2,3}. IR is now routinely used for analyses of a wide range of materials in laboratory and process control applications in agriculture, food and feed technology, geology and biomedicine (Shepherd and Walsh, 2004; 2007).

Standard error: the standard deviation of the sampling distribution of a statistic. For example, the standard error of the sample mean of n observations is $\frac{\sigma}{\sqrt{n}}$, where σ^2 is the variance of the original observations.

Strata: see stratification.

Stratification: the division of a population into parts known as strata, particularly for the purpose of drawing a sample.

Stratified random sampling: random sampling from each strata of a population after stratification.

Stratum: each subpopulation of strata.

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